

RIS-Aided NLoS Monostatic Sensing under Mobility and Angle-Doppler Coupling

Mahmut Kemal Ercan*, Musa Furkan Keskin†, Sinan Gezici*, and Henk Wymeersch†

* Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Bilkent University, Turkey

† Department of Electrical Engineering, Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden

E-mail: ercan@ee.bilkent.edu.tr

Abstract—We investigate the problem of reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS)-aided monostatic sensing of a mobile target under line-of-sight (LoS) blockage considering a single-antenna, full-duplex, and dual-functional radar-communications base station (BS). For the purpose of target detection and delay/Doppler/angle estimation, we derive a detector based on the generalized likelihood ratio test (GLRT), which entails a high-dimensional parameter search and leads to angle-Doppler coupling. To tackle these challenges, we propose a two-step algorithm for solving the GLRT detector/estimator in a low-complexity manner, accompanied by a RIS phase profile design tailored to circumvent the angle-Doppler coupling effect. Simulation results verify the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, demonstrating its convergence to theoretical benchmarks.

Index Terms—Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, monostatic sensing, non-line-of-sight (NLoS) sensing, angle-Doppler coupling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) have emerged as a transformative technology towards 6G with the promise of significantly boosting communication rates and expanding coverage through the ability to overcome signal blockages, especially in mmWave and sub-THz systems [1]–[3]. RISs also have benefits to improve sensing capabilities [4], [5], thereby supporting integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) [6]. Applications include monostatic [7], bistatic [8] and multistatic [9] sensing, as well as simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) [10]. RIS-aided sensing brings several important advantages over conventional sensing without RIS, such as RIS phase profile design for illumination of desired sectors [11], [12], non-line-of-sight (NLoS) sensing in the presence of obstacles [13]–[15], signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) enhancement [16] and high-accuracy angle estimation via large aperture of RIS [17].

In the context of RIS-aided sensing, several studies have focused on monostatic configurations [8], [13], [15], [18]–[21], particularly due to their attractive properties, including ease of synchronization and utilization of the entire signal (i.e., not only pilots). When the line-of-sight (LoS) path exists between the monostatic radar transceiver and the target, RIS can serve to boost the SNR via an extra, controlled path towards the target by judicious design of RIS element phases [16], [21]. Under LoS blockage conditions (as shown in Fig. 1), RIS can act as an additional anchor to provide high-resolution angle-of-departure (AoD)/angle-of-arrival (AoA) measurements of potential targets [13]. Given sufficient bandwidth (e.g., via

Fig. 1. RIS-aided monostatic sensing scenario under LoS blockage, where a dual-functional BS communicates with a user equipment (UE) in downlink (DL) while detecting a mobile target using the backscattered signals over the RIS path.

orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) transmissions [22], [23]), the monostatic radar can combine angular information with round-trip delay measurements over the RIS-induced NLoS path to perform high-accuracy localization of targets in a surveillance area blocked by obstacles [15].

A particular challenge arising in RIS-aided NLoS monostatic sensing pertains to detection and parameter estimation of *mobile targets*. In particular, target angle information can only be acquired through the RIS, which induces beamspace measurements at the radar receiver due to its passive nature (i.e., no sampling mechanism at the RIS), in turn requiring several non-parallel RIS beams [24]. In parallel, target Doppler is measured from slow-time phase shifts across transmissions. Consequently, the impact of mobility and RIS beam sweeping on slow-time phase shifts cannot be disentangled from each other, leading to the *angle-Doppler coupling* effect [25]. The few studies that considered RIS-aided sensing of mobile targets [14], [15], [20], [22], [23] focused mainly on RIS phase profile optimization and waveform design, ignoring the algorithmic aspects. Hence, the two compelling problems remain unexplored in RIS-aided NLoS monostatic sensing research: (i) detection and four-dimensional (range-Doppler-azimuth-elevation) estimation of mobile targets, and (ii) the accompanying problem of angle-Doppler coupling.

In this paper, we tackle the problem of RIS-aided NLoS monostatic sensing of a mobile target using the echoes of downlink signals transmitted by a dual-functional ISAC base

station (BS). We derive the corresponding generalized likelihood ratio test (GLRT) detector, which involves computationally complex four-dimensional parameter search over range-Doppler-azimuth-elevation domains due to angle-Doppler coupling inherent to RIS-aided angle estimation under mobility. To address this challenge, we propose to employ repetitive RIS phase profiles and devise a novel low-complexity two-step estimator that exploits the proposed temporal design to circumvent the angle-Doppler coupling effect, enabling separate estimation of delay-Doppler and azimuth-elevation. Simulation results reveal the effectiveness of the proposed phase profile design and the low-complexity algorithm in mobile target sensing.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we describe the RIS-aided NLoS sensing scenario, derive the signal model at the BS, and formulate the problem of detection/estimation of a mobile target.

A. Scenario

We consider the RIS-aided monostatic sensing scenario under LoS blockage as shown in Fig. 1, where a full-duplex dual-functional radar-communications BS with a known location performs monostatic sensing using the echoes of DL transmissions through the RIS-induced NLoS path [26], [27]. The aim is to detect a mobile target in the environment and estimate its parameters (delay, Doppler, angle). The BS is equipped with a single transmit (TX) and a single receive (RX) antenna, while the RIS has N_{RIS} elements. In addition, the RIS is assumed to have a known location and orientation.

B. Signal Model

For DL communications with a UE, the BS transmits an OFDM signal with N subcarriers and M symbols, with $x_{n,m}$ denoting the complex data/pilot on the n^{th} subcarrier of the m^{th} symbol. The subcarrier spacing and the symbol duration are defined as $\Delta_f = 1/T$ and $T_s = T + T_{\text{cp}}$, respectively, with T denoting the elementary symbol duration and T_{cp} the cyclic prefix (CP) duration. We assume the existence of a single target in the environment. To prevent intersymbol interference (ISI), the CP duration is assumed to be larger than the round-trip delay of the target over the RIS path [28]–[31]. In this setup, the backscattered OFDM signal at the monostatic sensing receiver of the BS on the n^{th} subcarrier of the m^{th} symbol (after removing the CP and switching to frequency-domain) can be written as [13], [14]

$$y_{n,m} = \alpha \underbrace{\mathbf{a}^{\text{T}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}})\boldsymbol{\Omega}_m\mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}_{\text{Target-RIS-BS path}} \underbrace{\mathbf{a}^{\text{T}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\boldsymbol{\Omega}_m\mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}})}_{\text{BS-RIS-Target path}} \times [\mathbf{c}(\tau)]_n [\mathbf{d}(\nu)]_m x_{n,m} + z_{n,m}, \quad (1)$$

where

- $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}} = [\theta_{\text{az}}^{\text{br}}, \theta_{\text{el}}^{\text{br}}]^{\text{T}}$ is the known AoA from the BS to the RIS.
- $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_{\text{az}}, \theta_{\text{el}}]^{\text{T}}$ is the AoD from the RIS to the target.
- α is the complex channel gain including the effects of (i) two-way attenuation over the forward BS-RIS-target path and the backward target-RIS-BS path, and (ii) radar-cross-section (RCS) of the target, which can be calculated as [15]

$$|\alpha| = \sqrt{\frac{P_t G_b^2 G^2 F^2(\boldsymbol{\theta}) F^2(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}}) d_x^2 d_y^2 \lambda^2 \sigma_{\text{RCS}}}{(4\pi)^5 d_{\text{br}}^4 d^4}}. \quad (2)$$

Here, P_t is the transmit power, G_b is the BS antenna gain, G is the antenna power gain of an RIS patch, $F(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = (\cos \theta_{\text{az}})^{0.285}$ is the normalized RIS power radiation pattern [32, Eq. (3)], d_x and d_y represent the RIS element spacing along the local horizontal and vertical axes, respectively, λ denotes the carrier wavelength, σ_{RCS} is the target RCS, and, d_{br} and d denote the BS-RIS and RIS-target distances, respectively.

- $\tau = 2(d_{\text{br}} + d)/c$ and ν denote the round-trip delay and Doppler shift of the BS-RIS-target path, respectively, with c denoting the speed of propagation.
- $\mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times 1}$ denotes the array steering vector at the RIS, given as follows [33]:

$$[\mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta})]_i = e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \cos \theta_{\text{el}} (\cos \theta_{\text{az}} p_{x,i} + \sin \theta_{\text{az}} p_{y,i})}, \quad (3)$$

where $p_{x,i}$ and $p_{y,i}$ denote the position of the i^{th} element in the horizontal and vertical axes of the RIS with respect to its center, respectively.

- $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_m = \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_m) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times N_{\text{RIS}}}$ is the RIS phase profile for the m^{th} symbol, containing RIS phase shifts $\boldsymbol{\omega}_m \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times 1}$ on its diagonal.
- $\mathbf{c}(\tau) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the frequency-domain steering vector as a function of delay τ , given by

$$\mathbf{c}(\tau) = [1, e^{-j2\pi\Delta_f\tau}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi(N-1)\Delta_f\tau}]^{\text{T}}. \quad (4)$$

- $\mathbf{d}(\nu) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the time-domain steering vector as a function of Doppler ν , expressed as

$$\mathbf{d}(\nu) = [1, e^{j2\pi T_s \nu}, \dots, e^{j2\pi(M-1)T_s \nu}]^{\text{T}}. \quad (5)$$

- $z_{n,m} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, N_0 N \Delta_f)$ is the additive complex Gaussian noise, with N_0 denoting the noise power spectral density (PSD).

To provide a more compact representation of (1), we define

$$\mathbf{b}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \triangleq \mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{a}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times 1}, \quad (6)$$

where \odot denotes the Hadamard (element-wise) product. Accordingly, we have

$$y_{n,m} = \alpha (\mathbf{b}^{\text{T}}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\boldsymbol{\omega}_m)^2 [\mathbf{c}(\tau)]_n [\mathbf{d}(\nu)]_m x_{n,m} + z_{n,m}. \quad (7)$$

We further introduce the collection of RIS phase profiles

$$\mathbf{W} = [\boldsymbol{\omega}_0 \cdots \boldsymbol{\omega}_{M-1}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times M}. \quad (8)$$

Using (8) and stacking over N subcarriers and M symbols, the model in (7) can be expressed in compact matrix form as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{X} \odot \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) \left(\mathbf{d}^{\text{T}}(\nu) \odot \mathbf{b}^{\text{T}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^{\text{T}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W} \right) + \mathbf{Z}, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ with $[\mathbf{Y}]_{n,m} = y_{n,m}$, $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ with $[\mathbf{X}]_{n,m} = x_{n,m}$ and $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ is the additive noise matrix with $\text{vec}(\mathbf{Z}) \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, N_0 N \Delta_f \mathbf{I})$. For ease of exposition, we assume that all the symbols are 1, i.e., \mathbf{X} is an all-one matrix. In this case, (9) becomes

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) \left(\mathbf{d}^{\text{T}}(\nu) \odot \mathbf{b}^{\text{T}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^{\text{T}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{W} \right) + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (10)$$

C. Problem Formulation

Given the frequency/slow-time observation matrix \mathbf{Y} in (10), our goal is to detect the presence of the target and estimate its delay τ , Doppler ν and azimuth-elevation angles $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Due to the angle-Doppler coupling over the slow-time domain (manifested through the terms $\mathbf{d}^T(\nu)$ and $\mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{W}$), this poses a computationally complex problem. To tackle this challenge, in Sec. III we derive a generic GLRT detector and propose a tailor-made RIS phase profile design, along with a low-complexity detector/estimator, to resolve the angle-Doppler coupling.

III. LOW-COMPLEXITY DETECTOR/ESTIMATOR DESIGN UNDER ANGLE-DOPPLER COUPLING

In this section, we first derive the GLRT detector for the sensing problem formulated in Sec. II-C, which leads to a high-complexity optimization. Then, we propose a low-complexity two-step estimator that avoids high-dimensional parameter search in solving the GLRT, by exploiting the structure of a tailor-made RIS phase profile matrix \mathbf{W} in (10).

A. GLRT Detector

To derive the GLRT detector, we re-cast (10) as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) + \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) \triangleq \alpha c(\tau) \left(\mathbf{d}^T(\nu) \odot \mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{W} \right), \quad (12)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\eta} = [\alpha, \tau, \nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}]^T$ is the unknown parameter vector. Note that the RIS phase configuration matrix \mathbf{W} is under our control, so we have degrees of freedom to design \mathbf{W} according to our needs for radar detection and estimation. The hypothesis testing problem for the model in (11) can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{Z}, & \text{under } \mathcal{H}_0 \\ \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) + \mathbf{Z}, & \text{under } \mathcal{H}_1 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

and the corresponding GLRT can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{Y}) = \frac{\max_{\boldsymbol{\eta}} p_1(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\eta})}{p_0(\mathbf{Y})} \underset{\mathcal{H}_0}{\overset{\mathcal{H}_1}{\geq}} \gamma \quad (14)$$

where γ is a threshold determined by a preset false alarm probability. In (14), the likelihood for the no-target case \mathcal{H}_0 is given by

$$p_0(\mathbf{Y}) = \frac{1}{(\pi\sigma^2)^{MN}} \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{Y}\|_F^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (15)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm and $\sigma^2 = N_0 N \Delta_f$, while the likelihood for the target-present case \mathcal{H}_1 is given by

$$p_1(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \frac{1}{(\pi\sigma^2)^{MN}} \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{Y} - \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta})\|_F^2}{2\sigma^2}\right). \quad (16)$$

Substituting (15) and (16) into (14) and simplifying, we obtain the log-likelihood ratio up to an additive and multiplicative constant:

$$\mathcal{L}^{\log}(\mathbf{Y}) = \min_{\boldsymbol{\eta}} \|\mathbf{Y} - \bar{\mathbf{Y}}(\boldsymbol{\eta})\|_F^2 - \|\mathbf{Y}\|_F^2. \quad (17)$$

In (17), the optimal channel gain can be estimated in closed-form as a function of delay, Doppler and angle parameters [34]:

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{\text{tr}\left(\left(\mathbf{c}(\tau)\mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta})\right)^H \mathbf{Y}\right)}{\|\mathbf{c}(\tau)\mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2}, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\mathbf{h}(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \triangleq \mathbf{d}(\nu) \odot \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{b}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{b}(\boldsymbol{\theta}). \quad (19)$$

Plugging (18) into (17) yields

$$\mathcal{L}^{\log}(\mathbf{Y}) = \min_{\tau, \nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}} \left\| \mathbf{Y} - \frac{\text{tr}\left(\left(\mathbf{c}(\tau)\mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta})\right)^H \mathbf{Y}\right)}{\|\mathbf{c}(\tau)\mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F} \mathbf{c}(\tau)\mathbf{h}^T(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \right\|_F^2 - \|\mathbf{Y}\|_F^2, \quad (20)$$

which can be simplified into (up to additive constants)

$$\mathcal{L}^{\log}(\mathbf{Y}) = \max_{\tau, \nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{\left| \mathbf{c}^H(\tau) \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{h}^*(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \right|^2}{\|\mathbf{h}(\nu, \boldsymbol{\theta})\|_F^2}. \quad (21)$$

In general, no further simplification is possible, so that a 4D search is needed to estimate delay, Doppler, and 2D angle.

B. Low-Complexity Estimator

To avoid the 4D search, we harness the possibility of designing the RIS phase profile \mathbf{W} in (11). With the proposed design, the observation model can be expressed in a form that allows separation of delay and Doppler. Then, the delay-Doppler estimation is described, followed by 2D angle processing. Finally, a refinement of the estimates and target detection are presented.

1) *Repetitive RIS Phase Profile Design:* The RIS phase profile is adjusted at each symbol duration:

$$\mathbf{W} = [\boldsymbol{\omega}_0 \cdots \boldsymbol{\omega}_{M-1}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RIS}} \times M}, \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})\boldsymbol{\omega}_0 \cdots \mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})\boldsymbol{\omega}_{M-1}] \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times M}. \quad (23)$$

From (11), we can see that the time-domain part of the signal depends on $\mathbf{d}(\nu)$ and $\mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{W}$. We will try to eliminate the effects of coupling between $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and ν . To this end, we can repeat RIS profiles consecutively. In that case, we use L profiles and repeat each phase profile M/L times:

$$\underbrace{\boldsymbol{\omega}_1 \boldsymbol{\omega}_1 \cdots \boldsymbol{\omega}_1}_{M/L \text{ times}} \underbrace{\boldsymbol{\omega}_2 \boldsymbol{\omega}_2 \cdots \boldsymbol{\omega}_2}_{M/L \text{ times}} \cdots \underbrace{\boldsymbol{\omega}_L \cdots \boldsymbol{\omega}_L}_{M/L \text{ times}} \quad (24)$$

With this design, during each time interval (i.e., M/L times), the phase shift caused by the angles is constant since the RIS profile is constant. Hence, we can eliminate the coupling effect during each time interval.

2) *Observation Model with Repetitive RIS Phase Profiles:* We will again use the signal model given in (11). But, to exploit the repetitive RIS phase profile on parameter estimation, we will use another form of (11) For that reason, we define

$$\mathbf{g}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{W}, \quad (25)$$

leading to

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha c(\tau) (\mathbf{d}^T(\nu) \odot \mathbf{g}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})). \quad (26)$$

Using the RIS phase profile with repetition, we can rewrite $\mathbf{g}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ as

$$\mathbf{g}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \underbrace{(\mathbf{b}^T(\boldsymbol{\theta})[\boldsymbol{\omega}_1 \cdots \boldsymbol{\omega}_L])^2}_{\triangleq \mathbf{g}_L^T(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times L}} \otimes \mathbf{1}_{M/L}^T. \quad (27)$$

Therefore,

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) [\mathbf{d}^\top(\nu) \odot (\mathbf{g}_L^\top(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{1}_{M/L}^\top)] + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (28)$$

Next, we define $\mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu) \triangleq [1 e^{j2\pi\nu T_s} \dots e^{j2\pi\nu(M/L-1)T_s}]^\top \in \mathbb{C}^{M/L \times 1}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\nu) \triangleq [1 e^{j2\pi\nu \frac{M}{L} T_s} \dots e^{j2\pi\nu \frac{M}{L}(L-1)T_s}]^\top \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$, which allows us to write

$$\mathbf{d}(\nu) = \tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\nu) \otimes \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu), \quad (29)$$

Plugging (29) into (28) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y} &= \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) \left[(\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \otimes \mathbf{1}_{M/L}) \odot (\tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\nu) \otimes \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu)) \right]^\top + \mathbf{Z}, \\ &= \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) \left[(\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\nu)) \otimes (\mathbf{1}_{M/L} \odot \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu)) \right]^\top + \mathbf{Z}, \\ &= \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) \left[(\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\nu)) \otimes (\mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu)) \right]^\top + \mathbf{Z}. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

With this, we are now ready to introduce $\boldsymbol{\beta} \triangleq \alpha \mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\nu) \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$, which will be a key to break down the 4D problem. With $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, we have that

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) (\boldsymbol{\beta} \otimes \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\nu))^\top + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (31)$$

By breaking up $\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{Y}_1 \dots \mathbf{Y}_L]$ we have that $\mathbf{Y}_l = \beta_l \mathbf{c}(\tau) \mathbf{d}_{M/L}^\top(\nu) + \mathbf{Z}_l \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M/L}$, $l = 1, \dots, L$.

3) *Delay-Doppler Estimation*: We estimate τ and ν from $\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_L$ by treating $\boldsymbol{\beta} = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_L]^\top$ as nuisance parameters. Due to the independence of noise across l , the maximum-likelihood (ML) estimator is expressed as

$$\min_{\tau, \nu, \boldsymbol{\beta}} \sum_{l=1}^L \left\| \mathbf{Y}_l - \beta_l \mathbf{c}(\tau) \mathbf{d}_{M/L}^\top(\nu) \right\|_F^2. \quad (32)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ can be obtained in closed form as a function of τ and ν , leading to

$$(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}) = \arg \max_{\tau, \nu} \sum_{l=1}^L \left| \mathbf{c}^H(\tau) \mathbf{Y}_l \mathbf{d}_{M/L}^*(\nu) \right|. \quad (33)$$

For a fast implementation, one can use FFTs instead of 2D search by performing 2D FFT of each \mathbf{Y}_l , integrating non-coherently across l , and taking the estimates as the corresponding peak point.

4) *Angle Estimation*: Given delay-Doppler estimates $(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu})$, we now wish to estimate azimuth and elevation angles $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_{az} \theta_{el}]^\top$ from the observations (see (30), repeated RIS phase profiles). We find that

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{c}(\hat{\tau}) \left[(\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\hat{\nu})) \otimes (\mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\hat{\nu})) \right]^\top + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (34)$$

Again, α can be solved in closed form, so that the ML estimator becomes

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \arg \max_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{\left| \mathbf{c}^H(\hat{\tau}) \mathbf{Y} \left((\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \odot \tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\hat{\nu})) \otimes \mathbf{d}_{M/L}(\hat{\nu}) \right)^* \right|^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_L(\boldsymbol{\theta})\|^2}, \quad (35)$$

which involves a 2D search over $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

P_t	10 to 40 dBm
G_b	18.06 dB
f_c	28 GHz
σ_{RCS}	2 m^2
N_{RIS}	21^2
d_{RIS}	$\lambda/4 = 2.7 \text{ mm}$
G	0 dB
N	1024
M	1120
Δ_f	120 kHz
T	$1/\Delta_f = 8.33 \mu\text{s}$
N_0	-174 dBm/Hz
Noise figure	8dB

5) *Refinement and Target Detection*: By using the estimates $\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$, we initialize a 4D search to solve the maximization problem in (21). After estimating delay-Doppler-angle parameters $(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\nu}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$, we plug them into the original GRLT expression in (21), yielding the detection test

$$\frac{\left| \mathbf{c}^H(\hat{\tau}) \mathbf{Y} \left(\mathbf{g}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \odot \mathbf{d}(\hat{\nu}) \right)^* \right|^2}{\left\| \mathbf{g}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) \odot \mathbf{d}(\hat{\nu}) \right\|^2} \underset{\mathcal{H}_0}{\overset{\mathcal{H}_1}{\geq}} \gamma. \quad (36)$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Scenario and Parameters

In the simulation setup, the center of the RIS is located at the origin, pointing towards the z-axis. We consider a point target 10 m away from the RIS with angle $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (45^\circ, 60^\circ)$, corresponding to $\mathbf{p}_{\text{tgt}} = [3.5355 \ 3.5355 \ 8.6603]^\top$ in Cartesian coordinates. The target has a velocity vector of $\mathbf{v} = [1, 0, 1]$ m/s, which results in a relative speed of $\nu = -1.22$ m/s with respect to the RIS. Also, the BS is located 5 m away from the RIS with angle $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{br}} = (135^\circ, 30^\circ)$, which corresponds to $\mathbf{p}_{\text{BS}} = [-3.0618 \ 3.0618 \ 2.5]^\top$.

We define the BS antenna gain similar to phased array antennas to choose realistic parameters. Commonly, phased array antennas have isotropic elements. In our scenario, we consider the case where BS has $N_{\text{BS}} = 64$ elements and has an antenna gain of $G_b = 10 \log_{10}(N_{\text{BS}}) = 18.06$ dB. We assume that the cyclic prefix is sufficiently long to avoid ISI. We generate our RIS phase profile to scan all the region behind the obstacle, which is a quarter sphere. In other words, we create equally spaced angular beams in the region of $\theta_{az} \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ and $\theta_{el} \in [0^\circ, 90^\circ)$. The other test parameters are given in Table I.

We vary the BS transmit power for the considered scenario and perform the following analyses. We run several Monte-Carlo tests for different transmit powers and different numbers of RIS phase repetitions. We perform 4D ML estimations as discussed in Sec. III-B, and calculate the GLRT using these estimates. To study detection performance, we perform the same procedure for noise-only signals with the same number of tests.

B. Results and Discussion

To evaluate the performance of the ML estimator, we calculate the RMSE based on Monte-Carlo trials and compare it with the CRB. The results are given in Figs. 2–5.

It is clear from the RMSE plots that the RMSE shows waterfall behavior and converges to the CRBs at high SNR, as

Fig. 2. RMSE of range estimation for $M/L = 2$ and $M/L = 5$ with CRB comparison.

Fig. 4. RMSE of azimuth estimation for $M/L = 2$ and $M/L = 5$ with CRB comparison.

Fig. 3. RMSE of Doppler velocity estimation for $M/L = 2$ and $M/L = 5$ with CRB comparison.

Fig. 5. RMSE of elevation estimation for $M/L = 2$ and $M/L = 5$ with CRB comparison.

expected. At low transmit power values, the RMSEs are upper-limited. The reason is that the values of the estimators are constrained. The range is limited to $[0, 1250]$ m, the Doppler velocity is limited to $[-321.4, 321.4]$ m/s, the azimuth is limited to $[-180, 180]$ degrees and the elevation is limited to $[0, 90]$ degrees. Additionally, we see that the RMSE of the range behaves similarly for both $M/L = 2$ and $M/L = 5$. That is because the frequency-domain steering vector is not affected and is constant for any RIS phase profile. Besides, we can see that the RMSE for $M/L = 2$ converges to the CRB later than that for $M/L = 5$ in Figs. 3–5. This results from the nature of our estimator. The objective function has several local maxima that are closer when M/L is higher, as shown in Fig. 6. In other words, the sidelobes are higher and are at a larger distance when M/L is smaller. Hence, the other local maxima can exceed the main lobe in the presence of noise, and the estimates can converge to these points, resulting in some outliers, hence, large RMSEs.

Additionally, we obtain ROC curves to investigate the detection performance with respect to the false alarm rate, as shown in Fig. 7. Considering remote sensing applications, the false alarm rate is set to 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , and 10^{-4} in the figure. As expected, larger detection rates can be achieved if higher false alarm rates are tolerable.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we addressed the time-domain coupling of Doppler-angle. To solve the coupling, we designed the repetitive RIS phase profiles. Using the repetitive RIS phase profile, we provided a low-complexity target parameter estimator that estimates delay, Doppler, and angles. Then, we derived the GLRT for target detection. We generated a simulation environment for a specified single-target case to analyze its performance. We constructed the RMSE figures to show that the RMSE converges to the CRBs for sufficiently transmit powers. In addition, the detection performance was depicted to show that with higher transmit powers, we can detect the target's presence by having a reasonable false alarm rate.

REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Wu *et al.*, "Intelligent reflecting surface-aided wireless communications: A tutorial," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 69, no. 5, pp. 3313–3351, 2021.
- [2] Z. Chen *et al.*, "Intelligent reflecting surface assisted terahertz communications toward 6G," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 110–117, 2021.
- [3] E. C. Strinati *et al.*, "Reconfigurable, intelligent, and sustainable wireless environments for 6G smart connectivity," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 59, no. 10, pp. 99–105, 2021.
- [4] R. Liu *et al.*, "Integrated sensing and communication with reconfigurable intelligent surfaces: Opportunities, applications, and future directions," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 50–57, 2023.
- [5] S. P. Chepuri *et al.*, "Integrated sensing and communications with reconfigurable intelligent surfaces: From signal modeling to processing," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 41–62, 2023.

Fig. 6. Objective function for Doppler velocity comparison between $M/L = 2$ and $M/L = 5$. The other parameters are chosen as the exact target values.

Fig. 7. Probability of detection versus transmit power. Probability of false alarm is fixed to 10^{-4} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-1} .

[6] F. Liu *et al.*, "Integrated sensing and communications: Toward dual-functional wireless networks for 6G and beyond," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 1728–1767, 2022.

[7] H. Zhang *et al.*, "Metaradar: Multi-target detection for reconfigurable intelligent surface aided radar systems," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 21, no. 9, pp. 6994–7010, 2022.

[8] S. Buzzi *et al.*, "Foundations of MIMO radar detection aided by reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 70, pp. 1749–1763, 2022.

[9] W. Lu *et al.*, "Target detection in intelligent reflecting surface aided distributed MIMO radar systems," *IEEE Sensors Letters*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 1–4, 2021.

[10] H. Kim *et al.*, "RIS-enabled and access-point-free simultaneous radio localization and mapping," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, pp. 1–1, 2023.

[11] R. P. Sankar *et al.*, "Beamforming in integrated sensing and communication systems with reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, pp. 1–1, 2023.

[12] R. Liu *et al.*, "Joint transmit waveform and passive beamforming design

for RIS-aided DFRC systems," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 995–1010, 2022.

[13] X. Song *et al.*, "Intelligent reflecting surface enabled sensing: Cramér-Rao bound optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 71, pp. 2011–2026, 2023.

[14] Z. Esmailbeig *et al.*, "Cramér-Rao lower bound optimization for hidden moving target sensing via multi-IRS-aided radar," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 29, pp. 2422–2426, 2022.

[15] A. Aubry *et al.*, "Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces for N-LOS Radar surveillance," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 70, no. 10, pp. 10735–10749, 2021.

[16] S. Buzzi *et al.*, "RIS-aided monostatic MIMO radar with co-located antennas," in *ICASSP 2022 - 2022 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2022, pp. 4998–5002.

[17] E. Björnson *et al.*, "Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces: A signal processing perspective with wireless applications," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 135–158, 2022.

[18] E. Grossi *et al.*, "Radar target detection and localization aided by an active reconfigurable intelligent surface," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, pp. 1–5, 2023.

[19] X. Shao *et al.*, "Target sensing with intelligent reflecting surface: Architecture and performance," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 2070–2084, 2022.

[20] Z. Esmailbeig *et al.*, "IRS-aided radar: Enhanced target parameter estimation via intelligent reflecting surfaces," in *2022 IEEE 12th Sensor Array and Multichannel Signal Processing Workshop (SAM)*, 2022, pp. 286–290.

[21] S. Buzzi *et al.*, "Radar target detection aided by reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, vol. 28, pp. 1315–1319, 2021.

[22] T. Wei *et al.*, "Multi-IRS-aided Doppler-tolerant wideband DFRC system," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, pp. 1–1, 2023.

[23] Z. Esmailbeig *et al.*, "Moving target detection via multi-IRS-aided OFDM radar," in *2023 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf23)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.

[24] K. Keykhosravi *et al.*, "SISO RIS-enabled joint 3D downlink localization and synchronization," in *ICC 2021 - IEEE International Conference on Communications*, 2021, pp. 1–6.

[25] A. B. Baral *et al.*, "Joint doppler frequency and direction of arrival estimation for TDM MIMO automotive radars," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 980–995, 2021.

[26] S. P. Chepuri *et al.*, "Integrated sensing and communications with reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2211.01003*, 2022.

[27] X. Shao *et al.*, "Intelligent reflecting surface aided wireless sensing: Applications and design issues," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2302.05864*, 2023.

[28] R. F. Tigrék *et al.*, "OFDM signals as the radar waveform to solve Doppler ambiguity," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 130–143, Jan. 2012.

[29] M. Braun, "OFDM radar algorithms in mobile communication networks," Phd Dissertation, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, 2014.

[30] K. V. Mishra *et al.*, "Toward millimeter-wave joint radar communications: A signal processing perspective," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 100–114, Sep. 2019.

[31] M. F. Keskin *et al.*, "MIMO-OFDM joint radar-communications: Is ICI friend or foe?" *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1393–1408, 2021.

[32] D. Dardari *et al.*, "LOS/NLOS near-field localization with a large reconfigurable intelligent surface," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 4282–4294, 2022.

[33] H. L. Van Trees, *Optimum array processing: Part IV of detection, estimation, and modulation theory*. John Wiley & Sons, 2002.

[34] M. F. Keskin *et al.*, "Limited feedforward waveform design for OFDM dual-functional radar-communications," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 69, pp. 2955–2970, 2021.